

CONVERSATION AS A MEANS OF DEVELOPING DIALOGIC SPEECH

Bakirova Umida Bakhtiyor kizi

Gulistan State University Faculty of Pedagogy 2nd year student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8026768>

Annotation: The educator already in the younger group should ensure that every kid easily and freely enters into a dialogue with adults and children. It is necessary to teach children to express their requests in words, to answer adult questions with words. Those children who have been brought up in a children's institution (nursery, kindergarten) from an early age are bolder and more willing to communicate with others. This is facilitated by meetings and conversations between the teacher and the children before transferring them to the second junior group. However, even in this case, the educator should continue to develop and streamline the speech activity of children.

Keywords: Mastering the sound culture of speech, phonetic system, language tools, speech development, speech hearing, sound of objects.

INTRODUCTION

In working with children of middle preschool age, the educator already pays more attention to the quality of children's answers; he teaches them to answer both in a short and in a common form, without deviating from the content of the question. It is necessary to teach children to participate in an organized conversation in the classroom: to answer only when the teacher asks, to listen to the statements of their comrades. Children of six or seven years old should be taught to answer the questions more accurately; they should learn to combine the short answers of their comrades in a common answer. Children of six or seven years old should be taught to answer the questions more accurately; they should learn to combine the short answers of their comrades in a common answer. Teaching children the ability to conduct a dialogue, participate in a conversation is always combined with the education of cultural behavior skills: listen carefully to the one who is talking, do not be distracted, do not interrupt the interlocutor. However, adults (educators and parents) should remember that for a preschool child, mastering dialogic speech is of paramount importance — a necessary condition for the full social development of a child. The developed dialogue allows the child to easily come into contact with both adults and peers. Children achieve great success in the development of dialogic speech in conditions of social well-being, which implies that the adults around them (primarily the family) treat them with a sense of love and respect, as well as when adults consider the child, sensitively listening to his opinion, interests, needs, etc., when adults not only speak they themselves, but also know how to listen to their child, taking the position of a tactful interlocutor.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

If a child of five or six months of life sees an adult doing his own business, he tries to attract his attention by means available to him (buzzing, babbling). At the age of two, the child's

speech becomes the main means of communication with close adults, he is a "pleasant companion" for them. At the age of three, speech becomes a means of communication between peers. However, the study of how a younger preschooler (2-4 years old) reacts to a stranger: does he seek to establish contact? waiting? does not respond to communication? — revealed the following. If an unfamiliar adult does not address a child or expresses his location only with facial expressions and a smile, then only 2% of children try to get in touch with him. However, every eighth child of this age already responds to an active appeal. Psychologists believe that the sensitive (favorable in the sense of receptivity) period of speech development is the age of 2-5 years. And how, right before school, do we help a child to master his native language and speech functions (communication skills, the ability to clearly state what he feels, what he thinks about, what he learned)? How solid is what the children were taught in the classroom, i.e. what is the "quality" of their independent statements and the level of speech activity? You can answer these questions by comparing the speech of children of middle and older preschool age. Oral speech, both monological and dialogical, is characterized by brevity and simplicity of sentence construction, non-union connections, emotional spontaneity, intonation and figurative expressiveness of presentation: saturation with sayings, proverbs. It is necessary to develop children's ability to build a dialogue (ask, answer, explain, ask, give a remark, support); using a variety of language tools in accordance with the situation. To do this, conversations are held on a variety of topics related to the child's life in the family, kindergarten, with his relationships with friends and adults, his interests and impressions. It is in dialogue that the ability to listen to the interlocutor develops, ask a question, answer depending on the surrounding context. It is also important to develop the ability to use the norms and rules of speech etiquette, which is necessary to foster a culture of speech communication. Most importantly, all the skills and abilities that have developed in the process of dialogic speech are necessary for the child to develop monologue speech. Kindergarten teachers direct their efforts to ensure that children's speech is meaningful and understandable to others and that speech communication itself takes place in forms that meet the requirements for human behavior in society. The content of speech depends on the content of children's lives. A stock of interesting observations, impressions, experiences, thoughts with an educated need for speech expression enriches children's speech. In order to achieve the content of children's speech, we should not forget that they really like to play with words and sounds, but this is good in its place and at its time. Intelligibility of speech, as a result of clear thought, is achieved by the ability to speak with sufficient completeness and consistency. Working on the content and clarity of children's speech is at the same time working on the formation of a child's thinking and expanding his horizons. The requirements of the program in terms of teaching dialogic speech are mainly reduced to teaching children to use such necessary forms of oral speech as a question, an answer, a short message, a detailed story. These requirements are implemented mainly in the classroom. At the same time, for the development of dialogical speech, along with classes, speech communication of children with each other and with the teacher in everyday life is of great importance. Starting from the fifth year of life, it is possible to observe differentiated, depending on the situation and the topic of the utterance, the use of linguistic means. Thus, when speaking about natural phenomena, children use adjectives and adverbs 3-7 times more often than when describing the phenomena of social life. In statements about familiar, understandable phenomena of social life, the use of verbs is activated 2-2.5 times. There are few of them in statements about

nature (11-16%). Children also differentially use the grammatical structure of speech. The most favorable situation for including complex sentences in statements is where it is necessary to explain something to a partner in the game or an adult, convince him, prove it. A large number of complex sentences are found in children's stories based on the plot picture (17-20%). The increased activity and independence in activity in the fifth year makes it easier for children to master the functions of speech: communication with adults and with each other, the ability to clearly express a judgment, accompany their actions with speech. Thanks to this, in the fifth year, as never before in the following, speech activity is high. The child pronounces an average of 180-210 words during 30 minutes of play. Children have a great need to explain to each other what they see and know — 40% of the total number of reasons for statements. In these situations, children utter so many complex sentences that you will not hear from them even in very informative classes in their native language. The morphological structure of the utterance (in the sense of the frequency of use of verbs, adjectives, adverbs) is not worse than in the classroom.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Solving the problem of developing coherent dialogical speech of preschool children, it should be noted that conversation is one of the most accessible and effective methods used in preschool institutions for successful implementation.

A conversation is a purposeful discussion of something, an organized, prepared dialogue on a pre-selected topic. Conversation is considered in preschool pedagogy as a method of familiarization with the environment and at the same time as a method of developing coherent speech. E.I. Radina in her research revealed in detail the importance of conversation for the mental and moral education of children. "The conversations systematize and clarify the ideas received by the child in the course of his daily life, as a result of observations and activities." The value of the conversation lies in the fact that an adult teaches a child to think logically, helps to think, raises from a specific way of thinking to a higher level of the simplest abstraction. In conversation, the child should recall, analyze, compare, express judgments and draw conclusions, conclusions. In conversation, along with thinking, speech develops. Speaking out in conversation, the child formulates his thoughts not in one, but in several sentences. The speech activity of a child in a conversation differs from a conversation, first of all by internal programming, thinking over his utterance, greater arbitrariness. Children learn speech-proof, the ability to justify their point of view, to enter into a "discussion". The content of the conversation is the program material for familiarizing children with the surrounding life: life and work of people, events social life, the activities of children in kindergarten. Conversations contribute to solving the problems of comprehensive development and upbringing of a pre-school child, accessible, psychologically close to him.

It is possible to systematize knowledge in a conversation under the condition of a clear, consistent arrangement of the material, i.e. with proper design. E.I. Radina identified such "structural components of the conversation as:

- the statement of a living image in the minds of children at the beginning of a conversation based on the recollection of phenomena close to life experience
- analysis of these phenomena during the conversation, highlighting the most significant details leading to conclusions

- an elementary generalization that clarifies the ideas of children, contributes to the development of an appropriate attitude to phenomena and stimulates children to certain behavior in the future."

Conversation is one of the most effective pedagogical methods in the work and education of preschoolers.

Conversation - in pedagogy, a question-and-answer method of teaching; it is used to activate the mental activity of students in the process of acquiring new knowledge or repeating and consolidating previously acquired knowledge.

"Conversation and conversations are essentially two almost identical manifestations of the same process: the verbal communication of people. But we, singling out conversations as one of the most valuable methods of speech development of children, mean by them organized, planned classes, the purpose of which is to deepen, clarify and systematize through the word representations and knowledge of children."

E.I. Tikheeva, a Russian teacher, one of the founders of preschool pedagogy in Russia, attached great importance to the conversation. She considered it "one of the most valuable methods of speech development of children, meaning by conversations organized, planned classes, the purpose of which is to deepen, clarify and systematize through words the representations and knowledge of children."

CONCLUSION

The methodology of formation of children's spoken language is dominated by recommendations for teaching a child to perceive adult questions and to answer them. There are studies on the other side of this problem - teaching children question forms of speech. Questions are an indicator of a child's intellectual development. The educator gives the children samples of the interrogative construction of sentences. "The following requirements for the conversation are highlighted:

In no case should the conversation pursue the goal of verbally planting knowledge in the heads of children. Its purpose is to systematize and consolidate the knowledge acquired by experience with a living word. In order for conversations to be lively and achieve the greatest result, it is necessary to strive to extract the independent thought of children, their personal attitude to the subject.

References:

- 1.Sokhin F.A. Speech development of preschool children. M., 1976.
- 2.Tikheeva E.I. Speech development of children, 1981.
- 3.Alekseeva M.M. Methods of speech development and teaching the native language of preschoolers:
4.a textbook for students of higher and secondary pedagogical educational institutions / M.M. Alekseeva, V.I. Yashina.
5.3rd ed., stereotype. - M.: Publishing Center "Academy", 2009 – 233 p.
- 6.Arushanova A.G. Formation of the grammatical structure of speech: speech and speech communication of children:
7.a methodological guide for educators / A. G. Arushanova. – 2nd ed., ispr. and add. - M.: Mosaic – Synthesis,
8.2011 – 322 p.

9.Borodich A.M. Methodology of speech development of children / A.M. Borodich. – M.: Enlightenment, 2008 – 231 p.

